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MANAGEMENT OF SOFT SKILLS AND ITS EFFECTS ON EMPLOYMENTS

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Abstract:

Recent research findings have reinforced the Importance of soft skills for managerial success. Consequently, there is an ongoing practical need for and research interest in effective soft skill training. In order to improve the soft skills of their employees, companies have begun to turn to performing artists in the hope of achieving a high training effect. While this phenomenon has created excitement, it has hardly been the subject of serious investigation guided by research questions and executed research methodologies. In particular, hardly any insights exist into the exercises artists use when providing soft skill training and coaching for a business audience. In order to explore such activities in a systematic way, this paper turns the attention to the performing arts higher education curriculum for identifying relevant exercise categories and for linking them to soft skills. However, the research has also limitations, especially a too conservative number of connections between performing arts curricular items and soft skill categories. These shortcomings are used for motivating future research.

Key Words: Management, Soft Skills, Employees, Coaching

1. Introduction

Each year, billions of dollars are spent by U.S. manufacturers to acquire hard and soft manufacturing technologies. Hard technologies are bundle of equipment, computer hardware and software such as computer numerical control, computer-aided manufacturing, robots, etc. In contrast, soft technologies are manufacturing techniques and know-how such as just-in-time, total quality management, statistical quality control, etc. - hardware is not essential to their successful use but can enhance their scope and effectiveness. This large empirical study of 1042 U.S. manufacturing plants develops a model to study the impact of manufacturing technology use on various performance measures; this study provides first evidence from the field that soft manufacturing technologies have many times the measurable effects of hard technologies on product, process, and business performance. Further, the effects of technology use are enhanced by the skilled use of technology. Implications for research and public policy are addressed. In the opinion of top management in manufacturing firms, soft technologies have an impact on 1) shop floor performance; 2) product line breadth; and 3) growth and profitability. These finding should make the investment in soft technologies easier to justify. If top management controls the purse, and if it sees a link between investment in soft technology and tangible benefits in these three areas, getting top management to invest in soft technology should be easier. Before deciding on requests for investments in soft technologies, we hope top managers would seriously consider the findings of this paper.

2. Soft skill models

The most simple soft skill models are those consisting of a list of relevant skills. Without any theoretical explanation or explicit justification, Crosbie (2005) offers a list of eight skills under the heading of soft skills. Other, somewhat shorter, single-list proposals can be found in Cockerill et al. (1995) or Davis et al. (1996, referenced in Hunt & Baruch 2003). As Figure 2-2 suggests, the skills (or rather skills categories) put forward by the two latter authors appear to be less concrete than the list provided by Crosbie. However, a simple correspondence analysis undertaken by the author of this thesis suggests that the soft skill sets proposed are by and large compatible (see the links in Figure 1).

Figure 1: comparing single-list soft skill models

Much of the soft skill related model tradition has not developed around notion of soft skills, but around the notion of competency (as pointed out earlier, soft skills can be regarded as a subset of competencies). Competencies can be defined as “the capability of applying or using knowledge, skills, abilities, behaviors, and personal characteristics to successfully perform critical work tasks, specific functions, or operate in a given role or position” (Ennis 2008: 4). Based on a literature review of competency models, Ennis specifies that “a competency model is a descriptive tool that identifies the competencies needed to operate in a specific role within a(n) job, occupation, organization, or industry” (Ennis 2008: 5).

A prominent competency model is the American Management Association (AMA) competency model (Powers 1983; Tobin & Pettingell 2008). Kline views it as a “validated competency model” (Kline 1986: 122). Table 2-3 shows the model in its most recent version. Here some guide lines can be acceptable:

Our company is put together with family and teamwork in mind; to this end, we treat our employees and clients like family. We will go the extra mile, work the extra hours, and put in the blood, sweat, and tears that you do to ensure your success.

- Today we enjoy success on both a national and local level. While many of our clients advertise nationally, we have chosen to not forget the little guy, the small business, the local merchant, as that’s where our roots are and that’s how our family started; to this end, we provide amazing packaged solutions for them as well.
- With over 1000 local companies and over 100 national and international clients, we have the experience necessary for any level of online marketing required of us.
- Our retention rate sits at 97% and most of our business is generated by referrals. This is a true measure of our commitment to our customers.
- We are one of the Top 10 Online Reputation Management Companies in the United States and we were recognized by Entrepreneur magazine for our efforts in this field.
- Our Total SEM solution has proved to be a highly successful and innovative solution, delivering a custom, packaged approach to online marketing in which we truly become an extension of your company and not just another vendor.
- Our Tealio Technology Platform was developed in-house to meet our growing client marketing needs and is currently in large scale development to be deployed as an agency or franchise solution and has received praise and major investment interest.

2.1 Manager - Soft lines - Arlington, TX

Description

- Responsible for smooth and efficient operation of assigned department.
- Responsible for managing personnel in assigned department including hiring, training, evaluating, disciplining, terminating.
- Recommend annual salary increases and bonuses for department associates.
- Perform reference checks on applicants.
- Complete new hire paperwork as necessary.

- Provide prompt, friendly customer service.
- Oversee department zoning, assist in zoning duties as necessary.
- Oversee department sign program.
- Oversee department price maintenance.
- Oversee housekeeping duties.
- Handle department communications.
- Responsible for auditing and filing of department paperwork.
- Ensure compliance with Academy policies and procedures to maintain a safe, productive environment for associates and customers.
- Manager on Duty (MOD) responsibilities when assigned.
- Required to learn company policies and procedures.
- Required to learn company safety rules.

2.2 Relocation Assistance Available.

Duties may change and associates may be required to perform other duties as assigned.

Qualifications

- 3 years retail experience required.
- 1 year management or supervisory experience preferred.
- Mobility Preferred
- High school diploma or G.E.D. required.
- Associate's degree in relevant field of study or equivalent years of related work experience preferred.
- Ability to work flexible schedule including nights, weekends, and holidays as necessary.

3. Relationships between soft skills related concepts

The soft skill related concepts treated in this chapter show considerable overlap.

Previous Figure shows exemplified links between the concepts of soft skills, emotional intelligence, communication, personality, leadership and charisma. The figure is not meant to suggest that there exist no other links or alternative interpretations than those made explicit. The more important observation is the immense interconnectedness among the mentioned topics: it is hardly possible to explore the research on one concept without sliding into the territory of the others. Figure 2 reinforces the sheer interconnectedness of the topics by showing how they reference 20 well-known behavioral concepts at the inter-personal and intra-personal levels.

4. Research goal 1: terminology clarification

The literature review has revealed that, in academia, the notion of soft skills has so far taken a back seat to related notions such as abilities, competencies and emotional intelligence. This contrasts with the well-established use of the soft skill notion in the practical business world, as witnessed, for example, by training supply databases (Training Marketing Service 2010). Sometimes provided by practitioners, soft skill definitions have been demonstrated in this thesis to be vague, incomplete or merely implicit (Georges 1988; Duncan & Dunifon 1998; Schiffer & Linde 2002; Muir 2004; Zellweger 2004; Klaus 2007; Rogmann 2008). Therefore, a working definition was created in this thesis to achieve terminology clarification and thereby fulfil the first research goal of this paper:

As distinguished from technical skills, soft skills are intra-personal and inter-personal abilities necessary for individual effectiveness or for effectiveness in interactions with other individuals in the workplace.

4.1 Research goal 2: soft skill set identification

Without exception, all consulting firms participating in the in-depth interviews rate the importance of soft skills as very high. This is because soft skills are critical whenever consultants deal with people throughout the consulting project's life cycle, including first client meetings, negotiation of consulting engagements, project kick-off meetings and presentations, such as the final presentation of consulting results.

In order to choose some general list of soft skills as a starting point, one can either turn to one of the few actual soft skill lists (Cockerill et al. 1995; Davis et al. 2006; Crosbie 2005) or extract those items from competency models that satisfy the soft skill definition (Ennis 2008; Tobin & Pettingell 2008). While such alternative soft skill overviews are mostly compatible or equivalent, it is not clear which skills can actually be trained by the means of stage performing arts exercises and which cannot.

Figure 2: Selected links between soft skills related concepts

The pilot interviews helped eliminate organizational-level soft skills, which did not seem addressable through performing arts training. Having identified the soft skill list of Crosbie (2005) during the pilot interview phase as a practical starting point, the main indepth interviews conducted with performing arts teachers, on one hand, and HR representatives from consulting firms, on the other, helped identify a list of seven soft skills transferable

from performing arts to management and needed in management consulting: communication, presenting, collaboration and teamwork, creative thinking, emotional intelligence, stress management and leadership.

Communication stands out not only as the most important managerial skill over the last three decades (Gentry et al. 2008), but also as the skill that is part of every performing arts exercise category applicable to non-artists. Management consultants require high levels of communication ability in their daily work, for example, when interviewing clients.

Presentation skills are highly important for consultants, because client presentations are the standard mode for delivering project results. Presentations can benefit from many performing arts exercises, which also support communication improvements - for example, language coaching, singing lessons or performance delivery.

The management consulting profession requires a high level of *collaboration and teamwork*, because every new consulting engagement potentially results in a new team constellation. Therefore, consultants need an ability to adapt quickly to new team constellations. In performing arts, ensemble settings, whether music based or theatre based, address the skill of collaboration and teamwork.

As witnessed by the in-depth interviews, *creative thinking* is a critical consulting skill, as creative solutions are a source of differentiation in the highly competitive consulting industry. Music and theatre improvisation have been identified, during the interviews with the performing arts teachers, as relevant exercise categories to improve creative skills.

As shown in the literature review, the concept of *emotional intelligence* has received considerable criticism. However, one can hardly deny the concept's acceptance in the practical business world, including the consulting profession. The empirical findings in this thesis suggest that consultants need emotional intelligence to read between the lines and put themselves in the shoes of their clients. Performing arts appear to be particularly suited to address skill development in this area through role-play or by working with music to stimulate or amplify emotions.

Stress management is important for consultants because of the immense pressure and the long hours of their work. While performing arts education knows no singular course dedicated to stress handling, the issue of stress is practically dealt with in many exercise categories including breathing, interpretation, performance technique and movement, dance and improvisation.

The more consultants progress in their careers, the more they need *leadership* skills for guiding junior consultants and client team members. The in-depth interviews with performing arts teacher's revealed simplified versions of music conducting exercises as a way of training some aspects of leadership, such as leading others through body signaling and breathing.

The set of seven soft skills presented above is the result of a two-stage filtering process that started with pilot interviews and continued with the main interviews. The same two-stage interview process has led to the exclusion of other soft skills such as "developing others" or "taking initiative". The soft skills that are positioned outside the transferrable soft skill set are either not demanded by consulting firms or not addressable through performing arts. Both the literature review synthesis and the in-depth interviews suggest that the list of seven soft skills does not represent a rigid typology. The skills are interrelated and sometimes overlapping. For example, communication has many links to other skills, since presentations, as well as emotions, are conveyed by means of communication.

4.2 Research goal 3: transfer clarification

The question of transfer clarification was addressed in the in-depth interviews with consulting and performing arts respondents along four aspects: benefit rationale, success factors, transfer content and transfer process.

5. Benefit Rationale

Because of the importance of soft skills for consultants, the majority of training at consulting firms is devoted to soft skills. The in-depth interviews with HR representatives from the consulting industry revealed the benefit rationale for considering the use of arts-based training beyond well-established training seminar programs. The six reasons identified for turning to performing artists as trainers were not only consistent among the two quite different respondent groups interviewed (performing arts teachers and HR representatives from consulting), but also compatible with literature (Buswick et al. 2004; Manning 2007b; Berthoin Antal 2009). Performing artists are felt to be *credible* masters of soft skills thanks to their education and their exposure to critical stage situations. They are credited with the ability to actually demonstrate skills rather than talk about it. Because stage artists must master a variety of skills simultaneously when on stage, arts-based training is assumed to be more *holistic* than conventional training interventions. Due to the superior analysis skills attributed to performing arts trainers, consulting firms imagine a high *training intensity and effect*. By using exercises from theatre or music performance, artistic interventions can address and amplify *emotional aspects*. Training participants from the business world may view exposure to arts as *innovative* and therefore be encouraged to try out new things in an unusual setting. Finally, arts-based training can be very *entertaining*, since artists can develop a sort of magnetism and have a fool's license.

6. Conclusions

This concluding synthesizes the results of this paper and reflects on the contribution to the nascent research domain of arts-based training in business. Section summarizes the research outcomes with respect to soft skill terminology clarification, soft skill identification, illumination of the skill transfer from performing arts to business and model construction. The contribution to professional practice and to interdiction is discussed.

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